

A traditional technique for obtaining 3D bioactive glass scaffolds with bone like structure

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Bone related problems are not a new issue in human life but they continue to rise with spreading of degenerative bone diseases in modern society. Synthetic biomaterials like bioactive glasses have a great impact in the field of orthopaedics and dentistry. Hench first discovered the ability of glass materials to create a bond with bones. Bioactive glasses¹ (silicate and borate based) like 45S5, 13-93, 13-93B3, 160S and 58S have the ability to form bone minerals, like hydroxycarbonated apatite (HCA), after immersion in simulated body fluid (SBF). Dissolution of ions (B, Cu, Zn, Mg, Co, Sr, Ca) from glass into the body fluid and increasing concentration of some particular ions contribute to the formation of the HCA layer. Moreover the release of such ions leads to the biological activity of bioactive glasses which act as a vehicle for the delivery of biologically active ions. Thus, current research often focuses on incorporation of such type of metal ions into bioactive glasses to enhance their bioactivity. Boron is one of the elements which plays a significant role in fast bone growth, i.e. it acts as a bone growth stimulating agent, being also an angiogenic agent². Boron modified 45S5 bioactive glass particles exhibit more pronounced bioactivity than the undoped 45S5 glass. Also, scaffolds made from bioactive glasses show great promise for bone replacement and regeneration in bone tissue engineering approaches. There is a need for the development of synthetic scaffolds for the repair of large defects in load bearing bones such as long limb bones. A number of methods like solid freeform fabrication, solvent casting, freeze casting, robocasting and foam replication is used to fabricate three dimensional (3D) scaffolds. Factors like porosity and pore diameter in the porous 3D scaffolds play an important role in the mechanical strength and bioactivity of the scaffolds. However, the scaffolds prepared by various conventional methods often lack the desired combination of porosity and mechanical strength for bone repair and regeneration.

In our present research work we applied a conventional tape casting method³ traditionally used in the field of ceramic processing for preparation of bioactive 3D scaffolds with highly interconnected porous microstructure. Firstly, we prepared the 13-93B3 bioactive glass with composition (53B₂O₃, 6Na₂O, 12K₂O, 5MgO, 20CaO, 4P₂O₅) by melt quench method. Scaffolds were prepared in the form of discs with the diameter of 10 mm using tape casting from organic suspension of glass particles. For this purpose the glass was ground and sieved to obtain glass powder with particle sizes $\leq 25\mu\text{m}$. Poly-vinyl butyral (PVB) and PEG-300 were then added to ethanol suspension of the glass powder with 25 vol% solid loading. The glass tapes were prepared with the use of the laboratory tape caster (Pro-cast, Hed International, New Jersey, USA). The thickness of the green tape was adjusted by the height of the Doctor's blade gap in the range between 200 to 250 μm . The sintering behaviour of the tapes was examined by heating the tapes at different temperatures with different holding times. The tapes were heat treated at 550 °C, 575 °C and 600 °C without holding time and also with dwell time of 1h, 2h, 3h and 4h. With increasing the sintering temperature and

holding time it was observed that tapes sintered at 575 °C for 1h sintered better (lower residual porosity) than tapes sintered at 550 °C with the same holding time. The tapes were completely sintered with no residual porosity at 600°C with holding time of 1h. As completely sintered tapes are not useful as scaffolds for bone regeneration, the heat treatment profile of 550 °C with holding time 1h was selected for further experiments. XRD results confirmed that crystalline phases were formed during heat treatment in the temperature interval studied. This formation is crucial, as the formation of crystalline phases in scaffold materials can reduce their bioactivity but also increase the mechanical strength of the scaffold. The tapes were cut into circular discs and stacked (10 tapes) together using a hydraulic press at an applied pressure of 6 MPa. The stacks were heat treated using the heat treatment profile specified above.

In our future work PMMA microspheres with diameter ranging from 106 to 125 µm (Cospheric, USA) will be added to suspensions in order to prepare tapes with controlled porosity, which will be further used as building blocks for preparation of porous scaffolds. The bioactivity of these scaffolds will be tested *in vitro*, in the SBF according to Kokubo et. al.⁴ Based upon the results of the *in vitro* analysis, *in vivo* studies are envisaged on selected scaffolds. The final objective is to evaluate the mechanical response and bioactivity of the scaffolds after implantation in the animal body.

References:

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